
ENHANCING DEVELOPMENT FLEXIBILITY: A GREY-BOX STRATEGY FOR ADAPTING TO UNFORESEEN ADVERSE CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

This work introduces an approach to adapt the corridors of the solution space methodology using a grey-box strategy. The need arises when developed components fail to meet the requirements set by the solution space methodology. For example, when additional constraints, such as shape-related conditions, come into play, they render it impossible to find feasible designs. Our two-step approach addresses this challenge: (1) given a parametrized component, identify feasible configurations of the component; (2) change the corridors to find better overall feasible areas. To identify feasible areas, we use Active Learning Reliability to train a classifier to identify feasible configurations. To change the corridors, we add a set of extra conditions to the original solution space formulation. The extra conditions include the desired conditions on a corridor. We test the method in a crashworthiness study, wherein a component failed to fulfill all conditions from the solution space method. Through adaptation and looking into the feasible areas, we identify a set of corridors that all components fulfill. In the end, our methodology improves the solution space method for better support.

Keywords Solution Space · Active Learning · Systems Engineering · Crashworthiness

1 Introduction

The automotive industry is shifting from only mechanical parts production to more IT-oriented solutions, driven by the need for advanced sensors and control units for vehicle performance and safety [1]. This shift has led to the adoption of Agile methodologies. These methodologies were originally designed for the software industry to address management challenges and improve product quality [2]. They are characterized by small incremental steps in development. In the past few years, these methodologies have been integrated into automotive software to achieve a more lean development. For example, Volvo Cars has adopted the methodologies and reported positive experiences with the Agile framework [3], positively supporting the adoption of these methodologies in the industry [4]. The adoption of Agile frameworks yields the need for a new set of systems engineering tools. The traditional tools used for supporting the development, such as the V-model, are not fully compatible with an Agile framework due to their rigid early-stage planning [5]. This is because these tools define sets of requirements each component must fulfill in the early stages without the possibility of changing them later in the development.

A first hint of the need for more flexibility during development was the introduction of the solution space methodology. The solution space method is a systems engineering tool that provides some flexibility during development. To do so, instead of defining a fixed local requirement, it defines a range for each local requirement within which the performance of each component must lay inside [6]. However, the solution space methodology also suffers from the same static nature as the other methods. If, on one side, the ranges provide better flexibility during development, on the other side,

they are fixed in the early-stage planning and never changed after. Therefore, as Agile methods demand adaptability and more flexibility throughout the entire development, and not just at the beginning, the static nature of the solution space method still poses a limitation to the adoption of Agile methodologies by the automotive industry.

This research aims to enhance the adaptability and flexibility of the solution space method in relation to an Agile framework by addressing the static character of the method itself. To do so, we identified two challenges: backfeeding information from the development to the ranges of the solution space method and forward-feeding information from the ranges to the development process. The first objective is to develop a method for updating the solution space ranges with the information acquired during development. The second is to create a methodology that relates the ranges of the solution space to the current design concepts. The combination of these two methods ensures that the solution space method is continuously updated and aligned with the development process.

2 Solution space method

The solution space method was introduced by Zimmermann and von Hoessle in 2013 [7]. Their aim was to address the limitations of the V-model approach in the automotive industry. To do so, the solution space method identifies performance ranges to express local requirements. Any design fulfilling these ranges is then considered acceptable. The introduction of these ranges itself solves the flexibility issues of the V-model. The solution space method allows a wider range of possible acceptable solutions, and by doing so, it also ensures that the fulfillment of the local requirement of these solutions is less sensitive to small design changes. Finally, the solution space also allows the development of the components independently of each other. Therefore, it allows the development to proceed faster.

2.1 General Formulation

Consider a product a company wants to develop anew. This product is made by a set of components that integrate physically to guarantee a certain performance. Beyond the overall performance, each component is characterized by a local performance that can be expressed as a function f of a set of performance parameters \mathbf{x} . The vector \mathbf{x} of performance parameters contains the performance parameters of all components, which, in the end, defines an n -dimensional design space Ω_{ds} of the overall performance of the component. The solution space method considers this design space and divides it into two subspaces: the feasible space Ω_{fs} and the infeasible space Ω_{is} . The feasible and infeasible spaces are defined in relation to a performance threshold f_c that each component must respect. In other words:

$$\Omega_{fs} = \{\forall \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_{ds} | f(\mathbf{x}) \leq f_c\}; \quad (1)$$

$$\Omega_{is} = \{\forall \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_{ds} | f(\mathbf{x}) > f_c\}. \quad (2)$$

The method then proceeds to identify inside Ω_{fs} a space where all performance parameters are independent of each other. This is equivalent to fitting an n -dimensional box, Ω inside Ω_{fs} . To guarantee maximum flexibility in local performance requirements, the volume of this box is maximized:

$$\begin{aligned} \max \quad & \text{vol}(\Omega) = \prod_{i=1}^n [x_i^u - x_i^l] \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \{\forall \mathbf{x} \in \Omega = I_1 \times I_2 \times \dots \times I_n = [x_1^l, x_1^u] \times [x_2^l, x_2^u] \times \dots \times [x_n^l, x_n^u]\} \subseteq \Omega_{fs}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Notice that $I_i = [x_i^l, x_i^u]$ is the i -th performance range associated to the i -th performance parameter allowed by the local requirements on a component. x_i^l is the lower limit of the range, and x_i^u is its upper limit.

To describe the design space and its two feasible and infeasible subspaces, thus being able to formulate and solve the optimization problem of Equation (3), there are two approaches: the indirect [8] and the direct method [9]. The first one is based on a sampling strategy of the design space. However, in the automotive field, this sampling approach is not common; therefore, we focus on the second one, based on an analytical description of the design space. This analytical description avoids sampling by fully expressing the performance function f through a set of equations. Avoiding sampling made this method particularly useful for complex systems like studying the crashworthiness of a new vehicle because evaluating a sample is generally expensive and time-consuming.

2.2 Crashworthiness Application

Applying the solution space methodology to cascade requirements for crashworthiness, such as those to guarantee the safety of the passengers during a frontal impact with full overlap, presents unique challenges. The crashworthiness requirements are generally defined by independent organizations to push manufacturers to make safer vehicles every

year. For example, for a frontal impact with full overlap, [10] defines in a protocol which criteria should be satisfied to fulfill their standard of safety during a crash. Although the document is lengthy and technical, we can simplify and reformulate the requirements stated in it into three fundamental points:

1. The vehicle must dissipate all of its kinetic energy K when travelling at 56 km/h (*minimum energy requirement*).
2. The vehicle must not experience a deceleration a exceeding 300 m/s² (*maximum deceleration requirement*).
3. The components in the front of the vehicle must deform sequentially from those in the bumper region to those attached to the firewall (*order of deformation requirement*).

Before being able to cascade these requirements, the direct solution space method describes analytically the design space Ω_{ds} . To do so, the approach uses a simplified modeling technique made of three steps [11]:

1. Analyze the structure of the vehicle, reduce it to the components that dissipate most of the energy, and build the Geometry Space Model (GSM) to describe the spatial relationships and connections between the components considered.
2. Reduce the components described by the GSM to their deformation lengths, divide the lengths into regular sections of s_i length to build the Deformation Space Model (DSM), and coordinate the sections based on when they are activated, i.e., identify in which order the components and their sections are deformed.
3. Assign to each deformation section a force level F_i as the performance parameter to describe the design space.

Given the simplified model and its set of performance parameters \mathbf{F} , we can proceed at defining the performance function f :

$$f(\mathbf{F}) = \begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^n F_i s_i \geq K \\ F_i \leq m_i a \\ F_i \leq F_{i+1} \end{cases}, \quad (4)$$

where m_i is the active mass at i -th section according to [12]. Thanks to the definition of $f(\mathbf{F})$, we can divide the design space into the two subspaces Ω_{fs} and Ω_{is} ; thus, compute the n -dimensional box Ω to find the set of force ranges expressing the local crashworthiness requirements on the components.

2.3 Flexibility Limitations

Despite providing the flexibility that is missing in the V-model, the solution space method has its own limitations. More specifically, there have been already several attempts to improve the flexibility of the method even further. For example, some methods propose to rotate the solution space box to widen the ranges [13]. Others propose to separate between early-stage parameters and late-stage parameters to allow the first one bigger ranges [14]. Newer approaches aim to give the development more power by letting it choose the range that fits the best [15] or to give the developers the ability to introduce local dependencies between parameters to customize the ranges [16].

These attempts highlight the limitations in flexibility remaining in the solution space method. In this work, we try to enhance the flexibility by introducing information that can be gained during the development process. We propose to either include this information in the formulation of the solution space method or link the information from the development with solution space ranges by propagating them to the physical design of components. Since we use the tools provided by reliability analysis for this last step, we briefly introduce the topic of reliability analysis in the coming section.

3 Reliability analysis

Reliability analysis quantifies the safety and reliability of engineering structures by estimating the probability of system failure due to uncertainties in manufacturing, operating, or environmental conditions [17, 18]. Central to this field is the limit state function, which is a function defined by its sign: positive when the studied system operates nominally and negative when it fails. More specifically, we consider an M -dimensional vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^M$ describing a set of parameters of the system and its joint probability distribution $\mathbf{x} \sim f_{\mathbf{X}}$, representing environmental and system uncertainties. How a system is operating is evaluated via the computational model \mathcal{M} . This model calculates a response quantity of interest (QoI) for the given system parameters \mathbf{x} . Then, the limit state function is defined as a function g negative when the system operates outside intended conditions, and positive when it operates nominally. Therefore, a common form is:

$$g(\mathbf{x}) = \rho_{adm} - \mathcal{M}(\mathbf{x}), \quad (5)$$

where ρ_{adm} is the maximum admissible QoI value before failure. This function partitions the input domain Ω_{ds} into a safe domain Ω_{fs} , feasible domain, and a failure domain Ω_{is} , infeasible domain.

The final purpose of reliability analysis is to estimate the probability of being inside the infeasible domain. Thus, it defines the failure probability P_f as:

$$P_f = \mathcal{P}(g(\mathbf{x}) \leq 0) = \int_{\Omega_{fs}} f_{\mathbf{x}} d\mathbf{x}. \quad (6)$$

However, estimating this integral is complex due to the implicit definition of Ω_{fs} and the costly evaluations of $\mathcal{M}(\mathbf{x})$. Traditional methods, which approximate the limit-state function with linear or semi-analytical methods, require many evaluations, making them computationally intensive [17]. To overcome this limitation, active learning strategies have been introduced to leverage the potential of machine learning and surrogate modeling. These methods construct an approximation \hat{g} using a small number of model evaluations. To reduce the number of evaluations, these methods focus on the transition area where $g(\mathbf{x}) \sim 0$.

Although there is a wide variety of algorithms to train \hat{g} [19], they all share the same base structure [20]:

1. Training an initial surrogate model \hat{g} with a small dataset evaluated from Ω_{ds} .
2. Estimating P_f and the confidence bounds using simulation-based methods.
3. Minimizing a learning function over the input domain to identify a new sample to evaluate and add to the dataset.
4. Evaluate, add the sample to the dataset, and retrain the surrogate.
5. Repeat steps 2-4 until a convergence criterion is met or the budget is exhausted.

What interests us the most is the capabilities of the method to position samples as close as possible to the area where $g(\mathbf{x}) = 0$ and create a surrogate accurate only in this area. The byproduct of these methods is, hence, a model accurate where the learned function changes sign. This model can then be used as an accurate classifier that requires a small dataset for training [21]. In the methodology we propose further below, we will use this approach to identify the good and bad design concepts in relation to the force ranges.

4 Enhancing the flexibility of the solution space method

This work investigates how to increase the flexibility of the solution space methodology by using the information gained during the development. The current solution space method does not include any mechanisms for updating and integrating information from the development without relaxing some of the initial hypotheses of the method itself, nor the ability to relate to the physical design of the system. We tackle both these two limitations separately, with two different methods, the first referred to as *feedback* and the second as *feed-forward*.

1. **Feedback:** this method integrates information acquired during development in the solution space method. We propose a method to impose development-driven conditions and re-compute an adapted set of performance ranges.
2. **Feed-forward:** the second method propagates the performance ranges to a physical component design. We exploit a classifier to identify the performance ranges computed with the solution space method in the domain of the design parameters of a system.

The overall set of methods proposed here represents a step toward making the solution space capable of adapting during development. Notice, though, that the methodology presented here is developed in relation to the application of crashworthiness of the solution space method. In any case, we expect the flexibility of the method to improve also in its general formulation, for any type of application.

4.1 Feedback: adapting the solution space ranges

Consider the design space Ω_{ds} and its division into Ω_{fs} and Ω_{is} . To adapt the ranges computed with the solution space method, we want to change the feasible space so that it also includes the input from additional development, hereinafter defined as user input. To do so, we define a space $\Omega_{fs-user}$, to include the user input f_{c-user} ,

$$\Omega_{fs-user} = \{\forall \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_{ds} | f(\mathbf{x}) \leq f_{c-user}\} \quad (7)$$

To then compute the new ranges, we fit a new n -dimensional Ω_{adp} box in the intersection of Ω_{fs} and $\Omega_{fs-user}$. Therefore, to maximize the flexibility, we solve the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \max \quad & \text{vol}(\Omega_{\text{adp}}) = \prod_{i=1}^n [x_i^u - x_i^l] \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \{\forall \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_{\text{adp}} = [x_1^l, x_1^u] \times [x_2^l, x_2^u] \times \dots \times [x_n^l, x_n^u]\} \subseteq \{\Omega_{fs} \cap \Omega_{fs-user}\}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Notice, that fitting Ω_{adp} is possible if the intersection between Ω_{fs} and $\Omega_{fs-user}$ is non-null. This means that if the user provides an input that yields a null intersection, the problem cannot be solved.

With this approach, the performance ranges the solution space provides can be changed according to any valid user input. Later, we will present an example to better understand how the computation is performed. However, notice that all the ranges of the performance parameters remain independent of each other. Not only that, the ranges computed are those that allow the biggest flexibility under the given conditions. We have achieved our original intention of having a custom set of performance ranges defined with the information coming from the development process, without compromising the independence between performance parameters and with the maximum possible flexibility.

4.2 Feed-forward: identifying feasible areas in the design parameters domain

To relate the performance ranges to the concept designs, we propose here a methodology to train a classifier capable of distinguishing between good and bad designs. To do so efficiently, we use an Active Learning Reliability methodology to create a small dataset capable of accurately approximating the border region between the two classes.

Consider a design concept and a set of design parameters \mathbf{w} a user can change the concept. We first define a limit state function $g(\mathbf{w})$ to relate the design parameters to the performance ranges. We define this function as positive when a good design is found, i.e., the performance ranges are all respected, and negative when a bad design is found, i.e., the performance of the component exceeds the performance ranges. For ease of explanation, we define this classifier directly for the crashworthy application. In this case, to measure the performance of a component, we use a finite element simulation of a single component being crushed. We then measure a set of force levels F_{avg} corresponding to the average value of force the component opposes when crushed over each deformation section. For example, consider the force-deformation curve in Figure 1, marked as a solid black line. This component in the DSM is divided into two sections, marked by the dashed lines. The force levels assessing the performance of the component are the average value of the force over each deformation section, as marked by the dashed line.

We can proceed to compare the force levels F_{avg} with the limits of the force ranges. A good design is when

$$F_i^l \leq F_i \leq F_i^u, \quad (9)$$

otherwise, the design should be classified as bad. Hence, we need a function that is positive when Equation (9) is satisfied. We can achieve this by defining the limit state function as

$$g(\mathbf{w}) = \min_{i=1, \dots, n+1} (h_i), \quad (10)$$

where

$$h_{i=1, \dots, n} = \min (F_{i, \text{avg}} - F_i^l, F_i^u - F_{i, \text{avg}}), \quad (11)$$

and

$$h_{n+1} = d_{\text{max}} - d. \quad (12)$$

This last function adds an implicit performance parameter on the total deformation length. The DSM defines how much each component is supposed to deform. Consequently, each component cannot deform more than the length established in the DSM, marked in Figure 1 as d_{max} . This last condition considers how much a component is deforming, i.e. the maximum span of the force-deformation curve marked as d in Figure 1, and compares it to d_{max} . Therefore, this function is positive if $d \leq d_{\text{max}}$.

Having defined a limit state function, we can train a surrogate \hat{g} . To do so, we recommend using the tools available in the open-source UQLab software [22, 23] with the setting reported in Table 1. The sign of \hat{g} determines to which class the designs belong, meaning that when $\hat{g}(\mathbf{w}) \geq 0$, the design represented by \mathbf{w} is good, otherwise it is classified as bad.

The methodology proposed here yields a classifier for the user to visualize the force ranges on their concepts and understand how different settings of their concept relate to the ranges. This helps in using the solution space method by bridging the gap between cascaded requirements and the physical design. By having this information, the solution space method now provides better insights into what designs are more likely to fulfill all of the requirements throughout the entire development and those that are more likely to fail.

Figure 1: Post-processing of crash simulation of a component. The solid black line represents the measured force-deformation curve during the crash. The vertical dashed lines represent the beginning and end of the deformation sections defined in the DSM. The dashed horizontal lines represent the upper and lower limits of the force ranges of each section (respectively F_i^u and F_i^l). The performance is evaluated with the average force level over each deformation section, marked as the solid horizontal line $F_{i,avg}$.

Settings	Option
Surrogate Model Function	Polynomial-Chaos-Based Kriging
Reliability Estimator	Subset simulation
Stopping Criteria	Maximum number of evaluations

Table 1: Details of the recommended settings to train \hat{g} in the open-source UQLab software [22, 23].

5 Practical example

To help the reader understand the two methodologies we proposed above, we present here an application to showcase the benefits of our work. For this purpose, consider the open-source model of the Honda Accord [24]. This model has been studied to be redesigned using the solution space methodology [12]. Therefore, in the front of the vehicle, seven components per side are identified as the main contributors to energy dissipation. These are highlighted in Figure 2a. For these seven components, the force ranges shown in Figure 3 are computed to fulfill the crashworthiness requirements introduced in Section 2.2. Moreover, in Figure 2b, the new concepts for these seven components are shown. For each component, there is a set of design parameters controlling how much energy is dissipated and the thickness of the metal sheets at different locations of the component. For the details on the computation of the force ranges, refer to [12].

5.1 Example of feed backward

Feeding backward information to the solution space method means adapting the force ranges computed previously. With the scope of presenting the methodology, consider Component 7 of Figure 2 and its force ranges shown in Figure 3. Suppose that because of external reasons, the ranges of this component conflict with the physical design of the component itself. Thus, the developers need to find a compromise with other requirements that are not included in the crashworthiness ones. For example, suppose that the developers want to shift the ranges of sections 25-28 with reference to Figure 3.

Figure 2: Honda Accord model on which the example is based on: (a) the original design of the front end of the Honda Accord with 7 components identified as important for crashworthiness; (b) the new conceptual design of the 7 components to re-design.

Figure 3: Force range (the white intervals) computed with the solution space method for the 7 components of the Honda Accord to be redesigned.

The first step to adapt the force ranges is to define the user-defined feasible space, $\Omega_{fs-user}$. In this case, this can be defined by the following set of equations,

$$f_{user}(\mathbf{F}) = \begin{cases} F_{mid}^{25} = 41 \text{ kN} \\ F_{mid}^{26} = 15 \text{ kN} \\ F_{mid}^{27} = 9 \text{ kN} \\ F_{mid}^{28} = 7 \text{ kN} \end{cases} . \quad (13)$$

In this equation, F_{mid}^i is the central value of the force range of the i -th section. This means that the user-defined condition is imposing the force range to be centered in the force level specified.

The space $\Omega_{fs-user}$ described by these user-defined conditions yields a non-null intersection with the feasible space defined by the cascade of crashworthiness requirements. Therefore, we can proceed with the second step, which is to re-compute the force ranges to fulfill the conditions requested by the developers. Therefore, we solve the following optimization problem,

$$\begin{aligned} \max \quad & \text{vol}(\Omega_{adp}) = \prod_{i=1}^n [F_i^u - F_i^l] \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \{\forall \mathbf{F} \in \Omega_{adp} = [F_1^l, F_1^u] \times [F_2^l, F_2^u] \times \dots \times [F_n^l, F_n^u]\} \subseteq \{\Omega_{fs} \cap \Omega_{fs-user}\} . \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The solution to the optimization problem in Equation (14) is shown in Figure 4. The new set of force ranges maintains the independence between performance parameters, unlike other approaches that want to increase flexibility or adapt the ranges [16]. However, it must be noted that, despite incorporating development data, the corridor widths have

Component	Parameters
1	$m = [90, 1500]$ kg, $t_{i=1,\dots,9} = [0.7, 3.0]$ mm
2	$m = [81, 810]$ kg, $t_{i=1,\dots,4} = [0.7, 3.0]$ mm
3	$m = [15, 300]$ kg, $t_{i=1,2} = [0.7, 3.0]$ mm
4	$m = [20, 200]$ kg, $t_{i=1,2} = [0.7, 4.0]$ mm
5	$m = [23, 300]$ kg, $t_{i=1,2,3} = [0.7, 4.0]$ mm
6	$m = [100, 230]$ kg, $t_{i=1,\dots,4} = [0.7, 4.0]$ mm
7	$m = [150, 200]$ kg, $t_{i=1,\dots,7} = [0.7, 4.0]$ mm

Table 2: List of parameters controlled in each component.

notably decreased. If this then becomes a limitation for the development of other components, like components 2, 3, and 6, it should be evaluated by the developers themselves. To study this, they can use the methodology to feed forward information to study the effects of these changes in force ranges on their concepts. Let us see an example in the next section.

Figure 4: Force range (the white intervals) re-computed under the user-defined conditions for the 7 components of the Honda Accord to be redesigned.

5.2 Example of feed forward

To apply the methodology to feed-forward information, we define a finite element simulation to test each component individually. This test is like a drop-tower test where each component is fixed on one side and crushed by a mass with a pre-defined mass and velocity. In these simulations, we control the shell thicknesses of different sections and the mass of the impactor, thus the energy of the impacting mass. Each parameter can vary within the relative design domain, as listed in Table 2. For each component, we train a different surrogate \hat{g} in order to have one classifier per component. Let us look at the trained model of each component.

Component 1

Component 1 has a total of 10 design parameters, 9 thicknesses and the impactor mass. To train the surrogate, we evaluated an initial dataset of 60 samples and then added 1.000 samples placed according to the active learning strategy. The trained surrogate is represented in Figure 5. As this figure shows, this component design yields good design only for small energies, meaning that the algorithm finds the area of good design for small values of the mass. A developer now knows that this component cannot dissipate much energy during a crash.

Component 2

Component 2 has 4 design parameters linked to the thicknesses and one to the impactor mass. We evaluated an initial dataset of 30 samples and then added 500 samples, which were placed according to the active learning strategy. The trained surrogate is represented in Figure 6. As this figure shows, this component design yields good design only for very small energies (small mass) and small thickness values in the first section. This means that this section of the component should be thinner than the others on average.

Figure 5: Surrogate model representing the areas of good designs (in grey) for component 1.

Figure 6: Surrogate model representing the areas of good designs (in grey) for component 2.

Component 3

Component 3 has a total of 3 design parameters. We started with an initial dataset of 20 samples and then actively placed another 300 samples. The trained surrogate is represented in Figure 7. As this figure shows, this component design yields good design only for small energies again.

Component 4

Component 4 also has just 3 design parameters, 2 thicknesses and 1 mass. To train the surrogate, we evaluated an initial dataset of 20 samples and then added 250 samples. The trained surrogate is represented in Figure 8. As this figure shows, this component design yields good designs for small energies. However, any combination of thickness can yield a good design. This means that these thickness values can be fixed arbitrarily.

Figure 7: Surrogate model representing the areas of good designs (in grey) for component 3.

Figure 8: Surrogate model representing the areas of good designs (in grey) for component 4.

Component 5

Component 5 has a total of 4 design parameters. Similarly to the other components, these are 4 thicknesses and one mass. The initial dataset is made of 25 samples, and the budget for the added samples is 400 samples. The trained surrogate is represented in Figure 9. As this figure shows, the area of good design is central to the design domain.

Component 6

Component 6 has 4 thickness parameters and one mass parameter. To train the surrogate, we evaluated an initial dataset of 30 samples and then added another 500 samples. The trained surrogate is represented in Figure 10. As this figure shows, this component design yields a good design region smaller than the previous components. This means that finding a good design for this component is more complicated than for the other components.

Figure 9: Surrogate model representing the areas of good designs (in grey) for component 5.

Figure 10: Surrogate model representing the areas of good designs (in grey) for component 6.

Component 7

Component 7 has a total of 8 design parameters. To train the surrogate, we evaluated a total of 860 samples, of which 60 are from the initial dataset, and 800 are added actively. The trained surrogate is represented in Figure 11. As this figure shows, this component design yields good design only for big values for the thickness parameters. This means that this component is expected to be stiffer than the others, as it would be expected by a component sitting close to the suspension and near the firewall.

6 Discussion

In this work, we propose two methods that can be added to the solution space methodology to enhance its capabilities. One of the methods proposes to identify the performance requirements defined by the solution space in the design space

Figure 11: Surrogate model representing the areas of good designs (in grey) for component 7.

of the design parameters. This approach enables the developers to understand the relationship between their conceptual designs and the requirements defined by the solution space method. Finding this relationship allows the users of the method now to understand how flexible their designs are when they are developing a new product. In other words, by looking at the results presented in Section 5, we can understand which components are more flexible throughout the development and which are less. For example, component 1 or component 4 can absorb only small amounts of energy, but their thicknesses can be arbitrarily fixed. Therefore, it is probable that these components will fulfill the requirements easily and can be designed in a more relaxed manner. Instead, components 6 or 7 have a relatively small area of good design. Therefore, finding good designs is more challenging, and they will require more attention.

Because of the extra attention some components need, it can be useful to change the force ranges of some sections. This is achieved with the other methodology proposed. This methodology allows for the change of the performance ranges without any relaxation of the initial requirements or independence between the performance parameters. This means that after the change, the development of the components can continue independently. However, this comes at a cost, meaning that the ranges on other components generally are narrower, thus making other components less flexible. The first method presented here, though, can assess if the reduced flexibility is problematic.

The combination of the two methods provides an overall increase of flexibility in the solution space methodology. First of all, the ranges can be changed throughout the development based on the information gathered during the development itself. These changes can then be transposed to a parametrized design. This allows to quickly understand the impact of the changes and steer either the design of the components or the adaptation of the ranges in a better direction. A direction in which there is a better understanding of where problems are originating in the physical design or in the requirements and independence formulation.

7 Conclusion

In conclusion, the methodology proposed here increases the flexibility of the solution space method. However, unlike other methods, the increase in flexibility is not linked to the ability to widen the performance ranges but to the ability to relate the ranges to the development. In other words, the proposed methodology bridges the gap between the requirements for the performance of a system and the physical design of the system. By filling this gap, the developers have more freedom to make informed decisions. The increase in flexibility is linked to the ability to better exploit the information contained in the solution space method and modify the performance requirements based on the knowledge gathered from the development itself. Thanks to our method, we expect the developers to be able to use the solution space methodology more throughout the development of a new product.

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